

Table 1. List of Protein Kinase Inhibitors approved by FDA.

(NRY, non-receptor protein-tyrosine kinase; RTK, receptor protein-tyrosine kinase; S/T, protein-serine/threonine kinase; T/Y, dual-specificity protein kinase)

Protein kinase inhibitor	Approval year	Primary targets	Target kinase family	Indications
Abemaciclib	2017	CDK4/6	S/T	Breast cancer
Acalabrutinib	2017	BTK	NRY	Lymphoma
Afatinib	2013	ErbB1/2/4	RTK	Lung cancer
Alectinib	2015	ALK, RET	RTK	Lung cancer
Avapritinib	2020	PDGFR	RTK	Gastrointestinal Cancer
Axitinib	2012	VEGFR1/2/3	RTK	Kidney cancer
Binimetinib	2018	MEK1/2	T/Y	Melanoma
Bosutinib	2012	BCR-Abl	NRY	Leukemia
Brigatinib	2017	ALK	RTK	Lung cancer
Cabozantinib	2012	RET, VEGFR2	RTK	Thyroid, kidney, hepatocellular cancer
Capmatinib hydrochloride	2020	c-MET	RTK	Lung cancer
Ceritinib	2014	ALK	RTK	Lung cancer
Cobimetinib	2015	MEK1/2	T/Y	Melanoma
Crizotinib	2011	ALK, ROS1	RTK	Lung cancer
Dabrafenib	2013	B-Raf	S/T	Melanoma; lung, thyroid Cancer
Dacomitinib	2018	EGFR	RTK	Lung cancer
Dasatinib	2006	BCR-Abl	NRY	Leukemia
Encorafenib	2018	B-Raf	S/T	Melanoma, colorectal cancer
Entrectinib	2019	TRKA/B/C, ROS1	RTK	Lung cancer; solid Tumors
Erdafitinib	2019	FGFR1/2/3/4	RTK	Urothelial carcinoma

Erlotinib hydrochloride	2004	EGFR	RTK	Lung, Pancreatic cancer
Everolimus	2009	FKBP12/mTOR	S/T	Breast, kidney cancer, Neuroendocrine tumors
Fedratinib	2019	JAK2	NRV	Myelofibrosis
Futibatinib	2022	FGFR2	RTK	Cholangiocarcinomas
Gefitinib	2003	EGFR	RTK	Lung cancer
Gilteritinib	2018	Flt3	RTK	Leukemia
Ibrutinib	2013	BTK	NRV	Lymphoma
Imatinib mesylate	2001	BCR-Abl	NRV	Leukemia; Gastrointestinal
Infigratinib	2021	FGFRs	RTK	Cholangiocarcinoma
Lapatinib ditosylate	2007	ErbB1/2/HER2	RTK	Breast cancer
Larotrectinib	2018	TRKA/B/C	RTK	Solid tumors
Lenvatinib	2015	VEGFR, RET	RTK	Hepatocellular, endometrial, Thyroid, Kidney cancer
Lorlatinib	2018	ALK	RTK	Lung cancer
Midostaurin	2017	Flt3	RTK	Leukemia
Mobocertinib	2021	EGFR with exon 20 insertions	RTK	Lung cancer
Neratinib	2017	ErbB2/HER2	RTK	Breast cancer
Nilotinib	2007	BCR-Abl	NRV	Leukemia
Osimertinib	2015	EGFR T790M	RTK	Lung cancer
Pacritinib	2022	JAK2	RTK	Myelofibrosis
Palbociclib	2015	CDK4/6	S/T	Breast cancer
Pazopanib hydrochloride	2009	VEGFR1/2/3	RTK	Kidney cancer; soft tissue sarcoma
Pemigatinib	2020	FGFR2	RTK	Cholangiocarcinoma

Pexidartinib	2019	CSF1R	RTK	Tenosynovial giant cell tumor
Pirtobrutinib	2023	BTK	NRV	Lymphoma
Ponatinib hydrochloride	2012	BCR-Abl	NRV	Leukemia
Pralsetinib	2020	RET	RTK	Lung cancer
Quizartinib	2023	FLT3/STK1	RTK	Leukemia
Regorafenib	2012	VEGFR1/2/3	RTK	Gastrointestinal, Colorectal, Hepatocellular cancer
Ribociclib	2017	CDK4/6	S/T	Breast cancer
Ripretinib	2020	KIT/PDGFR	RTK	Gastrointestinal cancer
Ruxolitinib phosphate	2011	JAK1/2/3, Tyk	NRV	Myelofibrosis
Selpercatinib	2020	RET	RTK	Lung, thyroid cancer
Selumetinib	2020	MEK1/2	T/Y	Neurofibroma
Sorafenib tosylate	2005	VEGFR1/2/3	RTK	Thyroid, Kidney, Hepatocellular cancer
Sunitinib malate	2006	VEGFR2	RTK	Gastrointestinal, kidney, pancreatic cancer
Temsirolimus	2007	FKBP12/mTOR	S/T	kidney cancer
Tepotinib	2021	Met	RTK	Lung cancer
Tivozanib	2021	VEGFR2	RTK	kidney cancer
Trametinib	2013	MEK1/2	T/Y	Melanoma
Trilaciclib	2021	CDK4/6	S/T	Lung cancer
Tucatinib	2020	ErbB2/HER2	RTK	Breast cancer
Vandetanib	2011	VEGFR2	RTK	Thyroid cancer
Vemurafenib	2011	B-Raf	S/T	Melanoma; histiocytic sarcoma
Zanubrutinib	2019	BTK	NRV	Lymphoma

Figure 1. Intracellular Signaling Networks Regulate the Operations of the Cancer Cell.

An elaborate integrated circuit operates within normal cells and is reprogrammed to regulate hallmark capabilities within cancer cells. Separate sub-circuits, depicted here in differently colored fields, are specialized to orchestrate the various capabilities. At one level, this depiction is simplistic, as there is considerable crosstalk between such sub-circuits. In addition, because each cancer cell is exposed to a complex mixture of signals from its microenvironment, each of these sub-circuits is connected with signals originating from other cells in the tumor microenvironment. (Hanahan and Wienberg [44]. With permission from Elsevier)

Figure 2. Therapeutic Targeting of the Hallmarks of Cancer

Therapeutic agents that can mitigate the acquired capabilities necessary for tumor growth and cancer progression are being developed for clinical use in treating different cancer types. These drugs are being developed in clinical trials to target each of the emerging neoplastic characteristics and the enabling hallmark capabilities towards effective cancer therapy. The listed drugs are just illustrative examples; there is a deep pipeline of investigational drugs in development to target different signaling molecules that lead to the hallmark capabilities. (Hanahan and Wienberg [44]. With permission from Elsevier)

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